

TRIBOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF A356 Al ALLOY – SiC_p COMPOSITE DISCS/BRAKE PAD TRIBOCOUPLE

R. C. Shivamurthy and M. K. Surappa

Department of Metallurgy, Indian Institute of science, Bangalore – 560 012, India

ABSTRACT

The dry sliding wear and friction behaviour of A356 Al alloy and 10 (C1) and 20 vol% SiC_p (C2) Al MMCs have been studied. In these tests, disc of Al alloy and Al MMCs and pins of brake pad were used. Wear tests were carried out at a load of 3 MPa and sliding speed in the range 1–5 m/s for a sliding distance of 15km. The effects of sliding velocity on the wear, friction and formation of tribolayer have been studied. Wear rates of Al MMCs as calculated by weight loss method, found to be negative at high sliding speed. Worn surfaces of pins and discs have been analyzed under Scanning Electron Microscope. SEM and EDAX analysis of worn surfaces of C1 and C2 disc shows formation of transfer layers consisting of mixture of oxides of Al, Si, Cu, Ca, Ba, Mg, and Fe and found to increase with sliding speed.

KEY WORDS: A356 Al alloy, Al MMCs, wear rates, brake discs, brake pad, tribolayers

INTRODUCTION

SiC particle reinforced aluminium matrix composites have been targeted for a variety of structural and tribological applications because of their superior properties over conventional materials. Al MMCs are well known for their high specific strength, hardness and wear resistance. Researchers around the world are trying to make use of these Al MMCs as a substitute for cast iron brake rotors in ground transport system [1–5]. However, efforts are under way to optimize the properties of both the disc and brake pad in order to achieve required wear and friction during braking.

Until now, most of the friction and wear data on Al MMCs have been generated from pin-on-disc tests. In all those tests, pins of Al MMCs are slid against hardened steel discs or cast iron disc [1–3, 8]. Information and data obtained from those tests [4] are of very limited use since, conditions prevailing are very much different compared to those in MMC discs/brake pad tribocouple. However, fundamental issues concerning the tribology of Al MMCs/brake pad tribocouple need to be better understood, in order to take maximum advantage of Al MMCs [6–7]. Hence, there is need to understand friction and wear performance and operating wear mechanisms during sliding of brake pads against Al MMCs discs.

The effect of sliding speed and load on formation of complex tribolayers on wear, friction of Al and its MMCs is studied and presented in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Unreinforced Al–7 wt% Si alloy (A1) and reinforced with 10 and 20 vol% SiC_p (40 μm size) and polymer based Volvo brake pad materials (PMCs) were used in present investigations. Al MMCs have been produced by stir cast technique. The polymer based brake pad material used in the present study was characterized by EDAX and X-ray diffraction methods. Both methods revealed that the pad material consists of several elements like Mg, Al, Si, S, Cu, Ca, Fe, Zn, and Ba.

From the as cast unreinforced A356 Al alloy and Al MMCs, discs were faced and turned using a diamond tipped tool in a lathe to a diameter of 70–72 mm, thickness of about 6–9 mm and a hole of 8 mm diameter was drilled at the center of each disc so that it could be able to fixed on to a pin-on-disc machine. Pins of 8×8 mm cross-section and height of 15 mm were made from pad materials. Dry sliding tests were conducted using Pin-on-Disc set up and tests have been conducted at a load of 3 MPa and speed in the range 1–5 m/s for a sliding distance of 15 km in a room temperature. Wear test procedure consists of pre test exercises like making sure that the pin bears applied load on its entire cross section, running in wear, wear test at intermediate load and intermediate sliding speed, followed by final wear tests at actual test conditions. This methodology was adapted for increasing accuracy of test data. During each test, wear debris were collected for further analysis.

Wear rate was calculated from measured weight loss of both the materials before and after the test. Friction coefficient was obtained by dividing the frictional force with applied normal load. SEM equipped with EDAX was used for analyzing and chemical constituents of worn surfaces of Al MMCs, PMCs and wear debris. Surface roughness R_a of both discs and pins used in dry sliding tests before and after was measured using SURTRONIC 3+ Profilometer. Initial R_a values of 1–3 μm on discs were obtained by grinding with emery 600 grit. Pin surface showed R_a values in the range 1–1.6 μm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

R_a values were in the range 0.9–1.3 μm and 1.1–2 μm on C1 and C2 discs and pins respectively. But in the case of A1 discs and pins, measured R_a values were in the range 5–11 and 5.4–14 μm respectively. The effect of sliding speed on the wear rates of disc (A356 Al alloy and Al MMCs) and pin are shown in fig. 1 and fig. 2 respectively. It is interesting to note from fig.1 that Al MMCs disc shows negative wear rates with increasing sliding speed. Corresponding wear rates of the pins increases with sliding speed. But in the case of A356 Al alloy, tests were stopped at different interval of times due to excessive wear of pin and consequently pin holder coming in direct contact with the disc. Therefore wear rate of A1 discs as well as pin wear rates decreases with sliding speed at a load 3 MPa. Variation in the coefficient of friction with the sliding speed is shown in fig.3 for A1, C1 and C2 disc/brake pad tribocouples. It was observed that, coefficient of friction decreases with sliding speed.

Worn surfaces of A1 consisted of smooth region and also abrasive grooves. At some locations combination of ploughing and micro cutting is seen. Typical SEM photographs of the worn surface of A1 disc is shown in fig.7a. Depth of groove decreases with sliding speed, which is not uniform over the worn surface. Some of the abrasive groove size is approximately 25–30 μm. There was no sign of transfer layers and debris formation was more. However, at all sliding speeds it was observed that very fine particles were present in small craters and contain Ca, S, Al Ba and Cu. Fig.7b shows the SEM photograph of the worn surface of pin. It consists of small number of micron size contact plateaus scattered over the surface. Severe fiber fracturing and edge cracking is seen at all sliding speed in worn surface of pin when it is slid against A356 Al alloy. All these point out high wear rate of pin.

Visual examination of worn tracks of Al MMCs disc shows that presence of shiny patchy layers across the wear tracks (fig.4). It shows the surface is somewhat rough and free from any abrasive grooves and ploughing. Fig. 8a and fig. 9a shows the typical SEM photographs of C1 and C2 disc respectively. Two kinds of tribolayers are distinguished from SEM examination, shiny appearance of copper rich layer and somewhat dark layers, consists of Ba, Ca, Si, Cu, In and Al. The extent of coverage of tribolayers on the wear track increases with the increase in sliding speed. The amount of copper and Ba in a tribolayers plays a predominant role in reducing the wear rates of composites (fig. 5 and fig. 6). Albeit the presence of copper, there was no stable transfer layer on A356 Al unreinforced alloy. The amount of debris formation was comparatively more in this case.

Fig. 8b and fig. 9b shows SEM micrographs of the pins, which were slid against C1 and C2 discs respectively. Pins, which slid against Al MMC discs showed relatively smooth surface and array of fibers, were intact. Examination of worn surface of discs and pins infer that correlation between wear data (obtained from weight loss method) and SEM analysis.

Fig. 1: Variations of wear rate of A356 alloy and its composite discs with sliding speed at a load of 3 MPa

Fig. 2: Variation of wear rate of pins slid against A356 Al alloy and its composite discs with sliding speed at a load of 3 MPa

Fig. 3: Variation of coefficient of friction with sliding speed at a load 3 MPa, A356 Al alloy and its composites

Fig. 4: Low magnification photograph of worn surface of A356 Al alloy-10 vol% SiC_P

Fig. 5: Variation in atomic % of Cu on wear track of A345 Al alloy-10 vol% SiC_P (C1 disc) and 20 vol% SiC_P (C2 disc) with sliding distance at a load of 3 MPa

Fig. 6: Variation in atomic % of Ba on wear track of A345 Al alloy–10 vol% SiC_P (C1 disc) and 20 vol% SiC_P (C2 disc) with sliding distance at a load of 3 MPa

Fig. 7: SEM micrographs of (a) A356 Al alloy disc (b) brake pad pin
Wear test condition: Load 3 MPa and sliding speed 4 m/s

Fig. 8: SEM micrographs of (a) A356 Al alloy–10 vol% SiC_P disc (b) brake pad pin.
Wear test condition: Load 3 MPa and sliding speed 4 m/s

*Fig. 9: SEM micrographs of (a) A356 Al alloy-20 vol% SiC_P disc (b) brake pad pin.
Wear test condition: Load 3 MPa and sliding speed 4 m/s*

CONCLUSION

Wear and friction behaviour of A356 Al alloy and Al MMCs have been evaluated using pin-on-disc setup at sliding speed in the range 1–5 m/s and a constant load 3 MPa.

1. A356 Al alloy-20 vol% SiC_P exhibits lowest wear rate followed by A356 Al alloy-10 vol% SiC_P and unreinforced A356 Al alloy at test conditions.
2. Absence of formation of tribolayers in unreinforced A356 Al alloy/brake pad results in higher wear rate of disc and pin, when compared with Al MMCs.
3. Wear rates of discs in A356 Al alloy-20 vol% SiC_P composite/brake pad tribosystems is extremely low and under most conditions wear rates are negative and the corresponding pin wear rates are always higher than the disc wear rates at all conditions.
4. Examination of worn surfaces of Al MMCs clearly indicates the formation of compact mixture of tribolayers including copper rich layers at all test conditions.
5. Tribolayers are adherent and appears to be stable and are responsible for the significant decrease in wear rate of composites.
6. Examination of worn surface of discs and pins infer that correlation between wear data and SEM analysis.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors wish to thank Department of Science and Technology, Government of India for financial support.

REFERENCES

1. Howell G. J., Ball A., “Dry sliding wear of particulate - reinforced aluminium alloys against automobile friction materials”, *Wear* 181–183, 1995, p 379–390.
2. Peter J. Blau, Harry M. Meyer III, “Characteristics of wear particles produced during friction tests of conventional and unconventional disc brake materials”, *Wear* 255, 2003, p 1261–1269.
3. Mohsen Mosleh, Peter J. Blau, Delia Dumitrescu, “Characteristics and morphology of wear particles from laboratory testing of disk brake materials”, *Wear* 256, 2004, p 1128–1134.

4. Shorowordi K. M., Haseeb A. S. M. A., and Celis J. P., "Velocity effects on the wear, friction and tribochemistry of aluminium MMC sliding against phenolic brake pad", *Wear* 256, issues 11–12, June 2004, p 1171–1181.
5. Osterle W., Urban I., "Friction layers and friction films on PMC brake pads", *Wear* 257, 2004, p 215–217.
6. Venkatraman B., Sundararajan G., "Correlation between the characteristics of the mechanically mixed layer and wear behaviour of aluminium, Al-7075 alloy and Al-MMCs", *Wear* 245, 2000, p 22–38.
7. Kwok J. K. M., Lim S. C., "High-speed tribological properties of some Al/SiC_p composites: I. Frictional and wear rate characteristics", *Composites Science and Technology* 59, 1999, p 66–63.
8. G. Cueva, A. Sinatora, W. L. Guessser, A. P. Tschiptschin, "Wear resistance of cast irons used in brake disc rotors", *Wear* 255, 2003, p 1256–1260.